

**International Journal of
Humanities, Educational and Literary
Research and Innovations**

A CBRTD PUBLICATION

Advancing Knowledge, Fostering Innovation

E-ISSN: 3115-5782

VOLUME 2 NUMBER 2; MARCH, 2026

**EFFECT OF MULTIMEDIA TEACHING STRATEGY ON ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN
MATHEMATICS, ENUGU STATE**

**OKPANACHI, Christiana Elejo¹, OBAJE Emmanuel Ayegba², ABDULKAREEM
Shuaibu² and ADEYEMI Olukemi Oluremi²**

¹*Department of Mathematics Education, College of Education, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Markudi*

²*Department of science Education, Faculty of Education, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Nigeria.*

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

OKPANACHI, Christiana Elejo

¹**Department of Mathematics Education**

College of Education

Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Markudi

elekristy123@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate the effect of multimedia teaching strategies on senior secondary school two (2) students' performance in Mathematics in Enugu State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated. The study adopted quasi experimental research design. The population of the study was 1,070 while a sample of 210 SS2 Mathematics students were drawn from four secondary schools using multistage sampling technique made up of 112 males and 98 females. The instrument of data collection was Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) and multimedia instructional packages (MIP). The instrument was trial-tested on 40 students. Kuder - Richardson 21 formula was used to determine the reliability coefficient of (MPT, $r = 0.77$). The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while ANCOVA tested hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics using MTS and students taught with the conventional teaching method. There was no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics using MTS. The study recommends that since multimedia teaching strategy has been found to enhance students' performance in Mathematics, Mathematics teachers should be encouraged to

adopt the instructional strategy for teaching topics in Mathematics. It was also recommended that Ministries of Education should incorporate the method in Mathematics curriculum.

KEYWORDS: Multimedia, Teaching Strategy, Academic Performance, Mathematics

INTRODUCTION

In most Nigerian Secondary Schools, Mathematics is one of the major subjects students take at internal and external examinations. The chief examiners report of West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) (2011) noted that Mathematics has the largest enrollment amongst other Science subjects such as Physics and Chemistry. Students apply the knowledge they get from studying Mathematics in solving many social and mental problems relating to application of knowledge in real life situations, developing scientific behaviour and attitude, health issues, environmental conservation, population and birth control. Mathematics lessons has gained more popularity and accessibility because of the availability of the Internet.

The advent of Internet, Worldwide Web and Information Communication Technology have made Mathematics even more popular as its teaching is no longer restricted to classroom or text book. This has also led to explosion of knowledge on Mathematics resulting in wide range of Mathematics literacy in the society as averred by Okpanachi et,al (2025). Despite the awareness about the importance of Mathematics to our everyday living, empirical evidence indicated by Abimbola & Abidoye, (2013) show that student's performance in external examinations like WAEC is still very low when compared with other Science Subjects Also, the chief examiners' report on WAEC for year 2010 - 2019 reflected the percentage grades of students in Mathematics WAEC examination which corroborates the failure rate, an indication that the educational goals and objectives set by the Federal Ministry of Education on Mathematics might not have been achieved which threatens the development of the nation. Gambari, Yaki, Gana, and Ughovw (2014) therefore opined that the implication of this failure in Secondary School Mathematics education could result in shortages of manpower in science and technology related disciplines which could affect Nigeria's vision to become one of the 20 industrialized nations in the world by the year 2030.

Several researchers like Yaki and Babagana (2016) have undertaken some studies to discover the causes of students' perpetual failure in Mathematics examinations. Njoku and Okoli (n.d) noted that among the causative factors of students' failure in Mathematics is Mathematics teachers' predominant use of ineffective teaching methods and inadequate material resources needed for effective delivery of Mathematics lessons. In most Nigerian schools, the major means of teaching Mathematics is usually the traditional method which can basically be classified into two: teacher-centered methods, which include lecture, lecture-demonstration, historical and pupil centered methods which include heuristic, assignment, project and classwork (Satyaprakasha & Sunitha, 2014; Asogwa, Muhammed, Asogwa & Ofoegbu, 2016). The persistent use of these methods by teachers has submerged the great potentials of students to be creative and innovative, and their ability to think critically and add their contribution to knowledge in the society. It also hinders meaningful learning from taking place. With several other challenges that the traditional instructional strategy has brought to the mathematics classroom, researchers like Katcha and Wushishi (2015), Satyaprakasha and Sunitha (2014); Aremu and Sangodoyin (2010) and many others have taken a close look at the problem and several of them had suggested that the participation of students in Mathematics lessons is very important to their understanding of the subject. It was thus suggested that teachers should use instructional strategies such as

multimedia, laboratory method, guided discovery learning that seek to arouse the interest of students, stimulate thinking and concretize concepts.

Multimedia is the combination of many media which are integrated in order to bring about better usage. It is the exciting combination of computer hardwares and softwares which allows the integration of video, animation, graphics, audio, and text resources to develop effective presentations on an affordable computer (Satyaprakashai & Sunitha, 2014). When more than two modes of instruction are used to present information which involves the use of words and pictures, it becomes a multimedia. Multimedia is presenting both in words (such as printed text as or spoken text) and pictures (such as illustrations, animation, photos, or video) together (Mayer, 2014).

Multimedia instructional package (MIP) is the use of appropriate and carefully selected learning experiences which are presented to the learner through selected teaching strategies which strengthen and reinforce each other so that the learner will achieve predetermined and desired behavioural objectives (Satyaprakashai & Yaspal, 2014). If teachers move from the traditional means of passing instruction to multimedia teaching strategy in the mathematics classroom, teaching and learning may be better enhanced and students' attention and interest could be better sustained. Since the multimedia is made up of different component, which may include: sound/audio, video/movie, animation, texts and graphic, great care must be taken while planning it for classroom lesson so that each of the component will be represented adequately without being mixed up.

Sound or audio can be in form of music clip, voice over, background music and transitional music. Okpanachi et al, (2025) noted that the sound effect gives life to the whole teaching process when it is becoming dull or unappealing It engages the interest of the students when used properly. It can also come in form of a narration to the graphics or animation that is being displayed which actually gives more meaning to the presentation. Sound can also provide emphasis on some important information to the students; it can be used as a means of transition from one page to another. Teachers can as well present a lot of information at once when the sound is well adjusted to screen display (Angadi & Ganihar, 2015).

Video clip has been viewed to appear real to students because of its ability to present the information in actual form. Ogochukwu (2010) inferred that videos are more beneficial to students due to its ability to take the students beyond the classroom experience. Videos can be used to give examples of phenomena or issues referred to in the text (Angadi & Ganihar, 2015).

Animation is another form through which multimedia can be presented. Pictures or objects are made to move in a way that can give meaning to students. This movement can be timed to accommodate the students' pace of learning; it presents the object of study to the students in a drawing movement form that best illustrates the demonstrated concept (Gambari, Yaki, Gana & Ughovwa, 2014).

Text makes a multimedia presentation adequate and understandable by its users. If texts are well-arranged, written and programmed and made to come in to the mode of presentation at the appropriate time, it gives better understanding to the students than using sounds and animation in the presentation (Angadi & Ganihar, 2015).

Graphics make room for creative possibilities during learning sessions in multimedia. They can be photographs, drawings, graphs from a spreadsheet, materials downloaded from the internet, or pictures from CD-ROM (Angadi & Ganihar, 2015). Graphics gives the pictorial view to the whole process and communicate the idea better to the student in picture.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

This study is based on the Cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML) by Mayer (1997) and the Dual-Coding theory as propounded by Paivio in 1986. CTML centers on the idea that learners attempt to build meaningful connections between words and pictures and that they learn more deeply than they could have with words or pictures alone. Mayer's CTML suggests that students can only process a certain amount of information at a time. Paivio describes two ways in which a man can expand on learned material, which are verbal association and visual imagery. The theory states that both verbal and visual information is used to represent information. Verbal and visual information are processed separately, and along different channels in the human mind. Empirical studies such as that by Satyaprakashai & Yaspal, (2014), showed that no single media can bring about meaningful learning in students, as a result the teacher must design the multimedia package in such a way that there would be integration between the chosen media. These media can be combined in various forms as much as it brings about meaningful learning in students,

Since the memory of each student is limited with quantity of information it can stored at any given time, this paper integrated sound (audio), animation and text. Multimedia instructional method helps students to process the same information in different media at the same time resulting in meaningful learning, which help learners to build adequate mental model, analyze the information and retaining it better than they do in the traditional classroom sessions (Okpanachi et al 2025).

Students' performance in Mathematics could either be low or high. It is low when the students do not attain up to the desired expectation or benchmark of the instructor, and high when the performance of the learners is exactly or above the desired outcome of the instructor. Several factors could be accounted for the low or high performance in Mathematics such factors include; the environment of the learner, learner's attitude, the nature of the subject, instructor, availability of textbooks and instructional materials, and the instructional strategy used by the teacher (Dinah, 2013). This implies that if students' performance in Mathematics will improve, new and innovative teaching method like multimedia Teaching strategy must be used to effectively teach the student in the mathematics classroom as it will avail learners the opportunity to see, view, and possibly hear instructions that are perceived to be difficult in Mathematics in simpler method.

- **Research Questions**

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics using MTS and those taught with CTM?
2. What are the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics using MTS?

- **Hypotheses**

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics using MTS and those taught with CTM

2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics using MTS.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the quasi-experimental design, using the non-randomized pretest- posttest, non-equivalent control group design. The population of the study consists of 1578 senior secondary school students of Mathematics (SS2) in two Local Government Areas of Enugu State. The SS 2 students were chosen because they are not currently preparing for any external examination, they are also familiar with Mathematics, and they have also been exposed to the traditional way of teaching Mathematics from SS1.

Four schools in the state were selected using multistage sampling technique; In each of the four schools selected, simple random sampling was used to select one intact class, the sample size for the study is 210 students, drawn from four schools two of which were designated experimental while the other two were the control. The experimental groups were taught with the Multimedia teaching strategy (MTS) while the control groups were taught using the conventional teaching method (CTM)

The instrument for the study was Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) which was adapted from WAEC past questions on topics that are related to the content covered in the lesson plans. The MPT consists of two sections, section A contains the background information on the respondents (class, time allowed and gender) while section B contains the questions. The trial-testing was carried out to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The result collected from MPT was analyzed using Kuder-Richardson 21 formula which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.77, this formula was used because the items were scored dichotomously MPT consists of 30 items which are multiple-choice objective questions with four options (A, B, C, & D) in which the students are expected to pick one they consider as the correct option. The total mark obtainable from MPT is 30 marks.

Multimedia instructional package (MIP): The lessons was designed by the researcher based on multimedia cognitive principles of learning as explained by Mayer (2005). The package was designed using the software package Scratch mBlock version (3.2.2) developed by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) media laboratories (2014). The MPT was used in teaching the experimental group after the pretest. The package includes content on unit 3 topics of Mathematics curriculum for SS2 students which are quadratic equations and inequalities, simultaneous equations, indices and logarithms with elements of Multimedia used in designing the package.

After the design of the MIP, the researcher gave it to an educational technologist specialist, three Mathematics teachers for face and content validity. The report from their observation was effected, on the package before taking it to the field, and it was trial tested on a representative sample of 40 SS 2 students.

The researchers and their assistants administered the pre – test to the students that participated in the study. Thereafter, the research assistants' taught Mathematics with MIP to the experimental group and conventional teaching method was used for the control group. The teaching lasted for four weeks after which a post- test (MPT) was administered to the students. Mean was used to answer the research questions, because it is a discreet data. Inferential statistics of Analysis of Covariance was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The choice

of ANCOVA is due to the fact that it statistically removes the initial differences across the non-randomized groups. This level of significance formed the basis for rejecting or not rejecting each of the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics using MTS and those taught with conventional teaching method.

Table 1: Mean Performance Scores of Students Taught Mathematics using MTS and those Taught with Conventional teaching method.

Group	N	Pre-MPT		Post-MPT		Mean Gain
		X	SD	X	SD	
MTS	108	6.78	3.30	20.82	5.62	14.04
Conventional Teaching Method (CTM)	102	7.57	2.91	12.60	3.29	5.03
Mean Diff.		0.79		8.22		9.01

Table 1, the result shows the mean performance scores of students taught Mathematics with MTS and those taught with convention method. The result shows that in the pre-test, the students taught Mathematics with MTS had a mean score of 6.78, while the students taught Mathematics with the conventional teaching method had a mean score of 7.57. The mean difference in the pre-test examination is 0.79 which is an indication that the two groups are having the same previous knowledge before the post-test examination. The result also shows that in the post-test examination, the students taught Mathematics using MTS out performed those taught Conventional teaching method.

Table 2: Result of ANCOVA of Performance Scores for Students Taught Mathematics Using MIP and Those Taught with CTM.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1072.104 ^a	2	536.052	9.572	.000	.135
Intercept	2820.617	1	2820.617	50.368	.000	.291
Pretest	880.283	1	880.283	15.719	.000	.113
T.Method	47.927	1	47.927	.856	.001	.007
Error	6888.031	123	56.000			
Total	559327.000	210				
Corrected Total	7960.135	207				

In Table 2, the result of the Analysis of Covariance shows that the P-value of 0.001 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significance. The result implies that there is statistically significant difference in the mean MTS. So, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected.

Research Question 2: What are the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics using MTS? Performance scores of students taught Mathematics with MTS and those taught without, are presented in table 3 below

Table 3: Mean Performance Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Mathematics using MIP.

Group	Pre-MPT		Post-MPT		Mean Gain	
	X	SD	X	SD		
Male	58	10.45	3.82	13.58	8.48	3.13
FEMALE	50	9.70	4.15	13.03	8.09	3.33
Mean Diff		0.75		0.55		0.20

In the Table, the result shows the mean performance scores of the male and female students taught with MTS. The result showed that in the pre-test, the male students had a mean score of 10.45, while the female students had a mean score of 9.70. The mean difference in the pre-test examination is 0.75 which is an indication that the two groups are at the same previous knowledge before the post-test examination. The result also shows that in the post-test examination, the male students had a mean score of 13.58, while the female students 0.55. This is an indication that both groups are at the same cognitive level after the application of treatment.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics with MTS.

To show if the performance of male and female students is significant, hypothesis 2 was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the hypothesis is presented in Table

Table 4: ANCOVA Result of Performance Scores of Male and Female Students taught Mathematics using MTS.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	90.908 ^a	2	45.454	.908	.408	.025
Intercept	4905.531	1	4905.531	98.008	.000	.576
Pretest	89.116	1	89.116	1.780	.186	.024
Gender	3.671	1	3.671	.073	.087	.001
Error	3603.759	72	50.052			
Total	321871.000	108				
Corrected Total	3694.667	102				

The result of the Analysis of Co-variance presented in Table 4 shows that the P-value of 0.079 is greater than the 0.05 level of significant at 1 degree of freedom. This shows that the hypothesis is not significant. The result implies that there is no statistical significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Mathematics with MTS. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the study in Table 1 and 2 showed there is a significant difference in the mean performance of SS2 students taught Mathematics with MTS and those taught without MTS. This implies that the experimental group improved on their performance in Mathematics than the control group. In this case, the study concludes that learning Mathematics using MTS improved students' performance in the subject.

The answer to research question two was provided on Table3. The result indicates the mean performance score of male and female students taught Mathematics using the MTS outperformed those taught mathematics using conventional teaching method. At the same time, analysis of covariance was employed for testing hypothesis 2, the F – calculated value for gender was 0.077 confirming that there was no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students in the experimental group. These might be because the two groups were exposed to the same instruction with multimedia and the lessons were captivating. The result of this study is in line with the findings of Gamabari *et.al* (2005), Aremu and Sangodoyin (2010), Katcha and Wushishi (2015), Oladele, (2019) who reported that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female students exposed to MTS.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the use of MTS enhances students' performance. This implies that the continual poor performance of students in Mathematics can be improved upon if Mathematics teachers adopt the use of multimedia teaching strategy as part of the teaching methods used in the Mathematics classroom. It is concluded that the use of MTS enhances student's performance irrespective of gender.

Therefore, the use of conventional teaching method alone should be discouraged.

- **Recommendations**

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this study

1. Ministries of Education, State Secondary school Education Boards and other Educational stakeholders are encouraged to promote the use of MTS in schools by organizing conferences, seminars and workshops for serving Mathematics teachers to learn or update themselves on the use of MTS.
2. Mathematics teachers should incorporate MTS in teaching Mathematics so as to promote and encourage social interactions, self-motivation and active engagement among learners
3. Curriculum planners and textbook authors should include MTS in Mathematics curriculum and Mathematics textbook as complementary to other teaching methods.

4. School Administrators and inspectors should ensure Mathematics teachers incorporate the use of MTS in Mathematics teaching.

REFERENCES

- Abimbola, I. O., & Abidoeye, F. O. (2013). Effect of qualification and experience of mathematics teachers on the status of ecology teaching in Kwara State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(24). Retrieved 22, 3, 2017, from [http:// www.iiste.org](http://www.iiste.org)
- Angadi, G.R., & Ganihar, N. N. (2015). Development and validation of multimedia package in Mathematics. Bridge Center Buzau, Al. Marghiloman 245 bis, 120082. Romania, European Union
- Aremu, A. & Sangodoyin. A. (2010). Computer animation and the academic performance of Nigerian senior secondary school students in Mathematics. *Journal of the Research Center for Educational Technology (RCET)*. 6 (2), 148-161.
- Asogwa, U. D., Muhammed, A., Asogwa E.N. & Ofoegbu, T.O. (2016). Effect of interactive Computer Simulation Package on Senior Secondary School Students Performance and Retention in Genetic Concepts. *Asian Journal of Information Technology* 15(14), 2313-2321.
- Dinah, C. S. (2013). Factors which influence academic performance in Mathematics in Kenya: A perspective for global competitiveness. *International Journal of Current Research*, 5(12), 4296-4300.
- Gambari, A. I., Yusuf, M.O. & Thomas, D. A. (2005) Effects of Computer Assisted (STAD), LTM and ICI Cooperative Learning Strategies on Nigerian secondary school students' performance, gender and motivation in Physics. *The Malaysian Journal of Educational Science*, 3(4), 11-26.
- Gambari, A. I., Yaki, A.A., Gana, E. S. & Ughovwa, Q. E. (2014). Improving Secondary school students' performance and retention in mathematics through video-based multimedia instruction. *A Journal of Scholarly Teaching*, 9(1), 78-91.
- Glomo-Narzoles, D. T. (2013). The effect of multi-media instruction on student learning. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 4(5), 126-130.
- Katcha, M. A. & Wushishi, D. I. (2015). Effects of laboratory equipment on secondary school students' performance and attitude change to mathematics learning in federal capital territory, Abuja, Nigeria. *Journal of Education Research and Behavioral Sciences*. 4(9), 250-256.
- Massachusetts Institute of Technology, media laboratory. (2014). mBlock softwear. Retrieved 10/10/2017, from https://www.media.mit.edu/project/sc_ratch
- Mayer. R.E (2014) (Ed). Introduction to multimedia learning: The Cambridge handbook of multimedia learning. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Mayer, R. E. (2005a). Cognitive theory of multimedia learning. In R.E. Mayer (Ed.), *The Cambridge Handbook of Multimedia Learning*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Mayer, R. E. (2005b). Introduction to multimedia learning. In R.E. Mayer (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of multimedia learning*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Michael-Aondoaseer, O. B., Adejoh, M. J., Okwara, K. O., & Uduaka, A. (2023). Effect of multimedia teaching strategy on academic achievement of senior secondary school students in biology, Benue State. *BSU Journal of Science, Mathematics and Computer Education (BSU_JSMCE)*, 3(2). 10 -19

Njoku, Z. C. & OKoli, J. N. (n.d). The gaps between teachers' classroom practices and mathematics education research findings in Nigeria: Need for Integration. *The Stemfest Journal*, 1-11.

Ogochukwu, N. V. (2010). Enhancing students' interest in mathematics via multimedia presentation. *African Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science Research*, 3(7), 107-113.

Okpanachi, C. E., Idoko, J., Achimugu, L. & Ode, J. (2025). "Effect of Multimedia Instructional Strategy on Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics in Enugu State" in *Journal of Science, Technology and Pedagogy*, vol. 3, No.1, Pp. 118-130

Paivio, A. (1986). *Mental representation: A dual-coding approach*. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.

Satyaprakashai. C.V. & Sunitha. B., (2014). Effectiveness of multimedia teaching on performance of VIII standard students in Mathematics. *International Journal of Informative and Futuristic Research*, 1(8), 59-60.

Satyaprakashai. C.V. & Yaspal S. (2014). Effect of multimedia teaching on performance in Mathematics. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research (IJEPR)*, 3(1), 41-45.

West Africa Examination Council (2010 - 2016). Chief examiners report, Lagos, Nigeria.

West Africa Examination Council (2011). Chief examiners report, Lagos, Nigeria.

Yaki, A. A. & Babagana, M. (2016). Technology instructional package mediated instruction and senior secondary school students' academic performance in Mathematics concepts. *The Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4 (2), 42-48.